

Jain Heritage Trail in Nayagarh and Puri Districts: A Historical and Archaeological Perspective

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Abstract

The districts of Nayagarh and Puri in Odisha are known for their rich religious traditions, predominantly associated with Hinduism. However, Jainism has also left its significant mark on the region through various archaeological remains, sculptures, and temple engravings. This study explores the Jain heritage in Nayagarh and Puri, documenting key Jain relics, their historical relevance, and their syncretic relationship with other religious traditions. The research is based on field visits, inscriptions, and an analysis of temple architecture that reflects the integration of Jain iconography into the broader religious landscape of Odisha.

1. Jain Heritage in Nayagarh District

Nayagarh district comprises the former princely states of Ranapur, Nayagarh, Khandapara, and Daspalla. Among these, the Ranapur and Nayagarh regions have yielded the most significant evidence of Jain antiquities.

1.1 Swapneswar Mahadev Temple, Ranapur

This temple, built in the Kalinga architectural style, consists of a *Rekha Vimana*, *Pidha Jagamohana*, and a *Bhoga Mandapa*. While primarily a Shaivite temple, it houses two distinct images of R̥ṣabhanātha, the first Jain Tirthankara, indicating the temple's historical connection to Jain traditions.

- a) **R̥ṣabhanātha I:** The *Tirthankara* with curly knots, and few strands of which are fallen over his shoulder, is in *kāyotsarga* posture over a double petalled lotus pedestal with the carrier Bull below the pedestal. The auspicious *trivali* mark at the neck, elongated earlobe, ornate *torana* surmounted by a circular decorated halo at his back and *chhatravali* capped by branches of *kevala* tree are the other features seen on the image. Besides, *aṣṭagrahas* (four on each side), *champakā* flowers and full-blown lotus flowers are represented on either side of the Tirthankara. He is flanked by chauri

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bearers at the bottom and flying *vidyadhara*s and musical instrument played in the hands of invisible *gandharva*s at the top.

- b) **Ṛṣabhanātha II:** The image is damaged at the upper portion of the stone slab. He stands in *kāyotsarga* posture over a double petalled lotus pedestal with carrier bull carved below. Twenty-four *Tirthankaras* (twelve on each side) in small size are depicted on either side of Ṛṣabhanātha (central figure). Ṛṣabhanātha is flanked by chauri bearers at the bottom and flying *vidyādhara*s at the top. He has a plain circular *prabhāvali* (halo) at the back of his head.

1.2 Kaunri Devi Temple, Gobindapur

This *Rekha Vimāna*-style temple houses several Jain relics alongside Hindu deities, demonstrating religious integration. Among the Jain sculptures preserved here is an image of *Ambikā* with *Yaksha Gomedha*.

The presiding deity is an eight-armed *Durga* locally known as *Kāmākshi thākurani* or *Kaunri Devi*. Other images found in the temple are *Vishnu*, *Pārvati* and Jain images of *Ambikā* with *Gomedha*.

- (a) *Ambikā* with *Gomedha*: *Ambikā* along with *Yaksha Gomedha* in *rajalilasana* posture are seated over a lotus pedestal. There are seven kneeling devotees below the pedestal. A tree is studded with flowers and a fruit is depicted behind them. A child is swinging in a swing is in the centre. *Neminātha*, the twenty-second *Tirthankara*, appears in *dhyānamudrā*. He is flanked by chauri bearers and garland bearers at the top. The temple is situated in the Gobindpur village on the side of Nayagarh-Khandapada Road. It is around 6 km east of Nayagarh town.
- (b) As understood, seven more Jaina images including the images of Ṛṣabhanātha (3nos.), *Parśwanātha* (1no.), *Ajitanātha* (1no.) and fragmentary Jaina *Tirthankara* (2nos.) were discovered recently from Ranpur area.

Besides the places having Jain sculptures as stated above, there are many important tourist places in Nayagarh district, like *Nilamadhav* temple (*Kantilo*), *Raghunath Jew* temple (Odagaon), *Ladukeswar* temple (Sarankul), Baramulla, Kunaria dam, Maninag of Ranapur, *Dutikeshwar Mahadev*, *Torabola* hot spring, *Ratnagada* waterfall, *Rajgiri* waterfall, *Jagannath* temple (Nayagarh), *Dakshina Kali* temple, Khandapara, Udayapur library, *Gokulananda Dashapalla* along with its adjoining areas.

The sites having links with Jains may be visited along with the above tourist sites of the district.

2. Jain Relics in Puri District

While Puri district is primarily known for Lord *Jagannatha* Temple, the region also contains notable Jain influences. This section documents Jain sculptures integrated into Hindu temple structures, indicating a historical overlap of religious traditions.

Jagannath Temple

A Jain *Tirthankara* image in chlorite stone and in standing *Kāyotsarga* posture is found in a small niche at the entrance (*Beharanadwara*) of the left wall of *Jagamohana* of Lord

Jagannātha temple. He has curly hairs with an *usnisa* at the top and is sitting over a double petalled lotus pedestal whose carrier is covered with the plasters. Chauri bearers decorated with ornaments stand in *tribhaṅga* posture in front of miniature *pidha* temple on the either side of the *Tirthaṅkara* at the bottom.

A circular *prabhavali* (halo) edged with lotus flower design is behind the head and a trilinear *chhatravali* is over the head. Behind the *Tirthaṅkara*, a *torana* decorated with flower and diamond motif is found. Flying *vidyadharas* with garland in hand and drums/cymbals played with divine hands are seen on either side of the *Tirthaṅkara* at the top. Champaka flowers are also found on either side of the halo.

Amruteswar Temple - Tala Beguniapada

It is a renovated *rekha vimana* and *pidha jagamohana* temple of *Kalingan* architecture. Along with Saivite sculptures, one will find a fragmented and head-less Jaina *Tirthaṅkara* image of *Sāntinātha* in *kāyotsarga* posture over a double petalled lotus pedestal. Out of *aṣṭagrahas*, five *grahas* are only traceable on either side of the *Tirthaṅkara* image. The chauri bearer with fly-whisk stands in *tribhaṅga* posture on either side of the *Tirthaṅkara*, at the bottom.

A two-armed *Sāsanadevi Mahāmanasi* seated in *dhyānamudrā* and lotus in the left hand and right hand is in holding elephants are pouring *bhumisparsamudra* is over a lotus flower and below the pedestal. Two figure is in the right and a conch in the left side of the deity are seen over lotus flower. A kneeling devotee is seen with folded hands in the water with pitchers over her head. A deer extreme right.

The temple is located on the left bank of the river Daya at the outskirts of the village Tala Beguniapada. It is around 16 km from Khordha on the right side of the road leading from Khordha to Pattanayikia chowk.

Achutrajpur

Many Buddhist and Jain images were found in the area while digging images of *Tirthaṅkaras* and *Sāsanadevis*, and one small chlorite image the area for the foundation of *Godavarish Vidyapitha*. Ten bronzes of *Ṛṣabhanātha* were found here. According to historians, the images may be of 8th-11th centuries AD. The bronze images are now preserved in the Odisha State Museum and one image of *Ṛṣabhanātha* is attached in the wall of Dakshya-Prajapati temple of Banapur.

The images kept in the state museum are *Ṛṣabhanātha*, Chandraprabha, *Vāsujyā*, Ambika and Ambika with *Neminātha*.

Balunkeswar Temple – Barala:

It is a *rekha vimana*, *pidha jagamohana* and *natamandapa* of *Kalingan* architecture. The *patalaphuta siva-lingam* within a circular *yonipith* is the presiding deity of the temple. In a separate small *pidha* temple attached to the inner wall of the temple compound, three images of *Ṛṣabhanātha* are preserved. They are in *jatabhara* hairstyle and have oval halo behind their heads surmounted with *chhatravalis*. They are in standing in *kāyotsarga* postures over double petalled lotus pedestals. *Aṣṭagrahas*, four on each side, flying garland bearer and cymbals/drums played with hands are depicted vertically one above the other on either side of the *Tirthaṅkaras*.

In case of the first *Tirthankara* image, the carrier bull is carved at the centre of pedestal and a foliated creeper flank on either side of the bull. In the second image the carrier bull is flanked by kneeling devotees with folded hands. The pedestal part of the third image is partially buried but shows kneeling devotee as well as flower buds. The temple is situated at the middle of the village *Barala, Sakkhigopala* tehsil. It can be reached from *Pattanayikia* chowk o Full blown lotus is also seen on either side of the *Tirthankara* image Bhubaneswar-Puri Road and is around 3 km east of the highway.

Sri Ramachandrapur:

In the shrine of the village *Rṣabhanātha* at the centre Goddess, a Panchatirthi image with found. *Pārśwanātha* and *Ajitanātha* an *Rṣabhanātha*. He is in *kāyotsarga* posture over a double petalled on the right and *Sāntinātha* and Mahavira are on the left side of lotus pedestal along with all the *pratiharys* including the carrier bull The other four *Tirthankaras* are flanked by their respective chauri bearers and mounts. The shrine is located at the outskirts of the village.

Many Jain metal images were found in Kakatpur area, which shifted to Ashutosh Museum of Indian art, Indian Museum (Kolkata), Odisha State Museum, Bhubhaneswar and District Museum, Puri.

Besides *Jagannath* temple, *Loknath* temple and other temples and beaches of Puri town, the district is famous for the tourist places such as *Konark*, *Chandrabhaga* beach *Baliharichandi* temple, *Alarnath* temple, *Satyabadi* (*Sakhigopal* beach, *Ramchandi* temple temple and *Panchasakha pitha*, *Barahi* temple, *Raghurajpur*, *Dandsahi*, *Pipli*, *Chilika* Lake with its tourist places, *Astaranga* sea *Balighai* sea beach, *Jahania* Pir, *Beleswar* beach, *Kakatpur Mangala* *Siruli Mahavir* and *Barla Balunkeswar*.

Conclusion

The Jain heritage of Nayagarh and Puri districts illustrates the cultural synthesis between Jainism and Hinduism in Odisha. The preservation of Jain *Tirthankara* images, *Sāsanadevis*, and temple engravings within Hindu temples reflects a shared religious history. Further archaeological research and conservation efforts are essential to safeguard these historical artifacts and promote Jain heritage tourism in the region. This study contributes to understanding Jain-Hindu syncretism in Odisha and provides a framework for future conservation policies.